

EPIC TRADITIONS IN BERDAKH'S WORKS

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Abstract. *The article studies the historical events in the life of the Karakalpaks as part of the Khiva Khanate: national liberation uprisings, the activities of Aidosbiy, his desire to create a separate state, his death as a result of the deceitful policy of the khanate, the disunity of the Karakalpak biys, the limitations of their worldview, the low level of national self-awareness, which served as an important factor in the creation of Berdakh's historical poems. The truthfulness and realism of the poet's works, aimed at the khanate system and representatives of the ruling circles, led to the persecution of Berdakh's epic dastans, and differences in their assessment. The poet's creative path and the poetic world reflected in the historical and epic dastans require a holistic and comprehensive consideration. By studying the problem of the poetic world of Berdakh and its historical roots using his historical-epic dastans as an example, the author comes to the conclusion that the national liberation uprising led by Aidos biy showed the courage and bravery of Aidos, who spoke out against the oppression of the Khiva Khanate, the policy of the khanate aimed at inciting national hatred; the changes that occurred in the life of the Karakalpaks under the influence of the policy of colonial Russia contributed to the deepening of Berdakh's artistic thinking, the expansion of the content of his historical-epic dastans.*

Keywords: *poet, epic traditions, epic tales (dastan), style, trope, dialogue.*

One of the classic poets who raised Karakalpak literature to a new artistic and aesthetic peak in the 19th century is the master of words Berdakh Gargabay uly. Epic traditions of folklore - the heroic cult, the unity of the people, the glorification of the struggle for independence - are the distinctive features of the tales (dastans) of Berdakh. The continuity of these traditions in the work of the poet Berdakh is associated with the historical, social, political and economic conditions of the era in which the poet lived - the second half of the 19th century, when very important events took place in the life of the Karakalpak people. Several nationalities, ethnic groups lived in the Khiva Khanate, whose way of life, national language, spiritual culture, literature were formed over the centuries. The decline of feudal relations had a significant impact on the people, led them to understand their economic interests, civil law, national identity. As a result, the peoples living in this khanate began to pursue a policy of preserving national unity. In this regard, such important events for the Karakalpak people as the uprising of 1827 led by Aidos biy, the struggle for the throne in Khiva in 1850, the Kungrad uprising of 1856, the capture of the khanate by the Russian Empire in 1873 took place. Under the influence of historical events, Berdakh created such dastans as "Akmak pat-sha" ("The Tyrant Tsar"), "Ernazar biy", "Aidos baba", "Amangeldi", "Kulen bolys", "Khorezm". Like other representatives of the progressive intelligentsia of that time, Berdakh reflected in his works his point of view on social life, the social system in which he lived. In the dastan "Aidos baba" the main idea becomes the idea of national self-awareness. Aidar Murtazaev writes that the author created this work in order to deal a crushing blow to some corrupt biys, cowards who bowed before the shadow of the khan instead of, like Aidos, going to the khan's accomplices with a sabre, giving them bribes, saying: "It is better to live for today," - and thereby

contributing to the fact that the people found themselves in a difficult situation. In the dastan "Aidos Baba" by Berdakh, unlike folk legends, it is not said that Aidos biy leads all the Karakalpaks living in the direction of "Mayly Shengel" and that his brothers Begis and Myrzhik do not want to obey the khan and resist.

The style of the dastan "Aydos Baba" retains some features of oral folklore, such as praise, dedication, description. In this regard, researchers of Karakalpak literature of the 19th century wrote: "Karakalpak poets in their works praised famous heroes who defended their homeland, fought for freedom, for the honor of their people, famous beauties, biys. As an example, we can cite the poems "Zhailauym" ("My Pasture") by Kunhoja, "Yellerim bardy", "Bardur", "Bir pari", "Saudigim", "Sa-daga", "Kyrmyzy" by Ajiniyaz, "Amangeldi", "Ernazar biy" by Berdakh, "Gulziyba" by Otesh." And in the dastan "Aydos Baba" features of the folk style are preserved. Aydos biy is described as a brave, keeping his word, great (famous) man. This reminds of the portraits of the heroes from the dastans "Alpamys", "Koblan", "Kyrk kyz" ("Forty girls"). Although the presentation of events, the description of the heroes of the works retain traces of the epic style, there is also some novelty. Berdakh wrote the dastan "Aidos Baba" in the form of a quatrain of Eastern poetry "Murabba". This form with the rhyme a-a-a-b in its rhythmic pattern and the number of rhyming syllables resembles the medieval syllabic quatrain of Turkic poetry, from which we can conclude that Berdakh, combining folklore traditions and book style, achieved their synthesis. In heroic dastans, the use of tropes has its own characteristics. Epithets, hyperbole, comparisons are widely used in creating the image of heroes. Traces of such epic descriptions are also found in Berdakh's work "Aidos Baba". Although the prototype of Aidos biy is taken from real history, life, in the description of his actions and behavior there are traces of epic elements.

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